

Differential pulse polarographic determination of thallium at trace level

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Optimal voltammetric conditions have been developed for micro-level determination of thallium by differential pulse polarography in presence of copper, cadmium and zinc. The limit of determination achieved is $50 \mu\text{g dm}^{-3}$.

Electrochemical stripping methods¹ based on voltammetric or potentiometric detection are seemed to be feasible principal approaches for the determination of thallium in different matrices. Svancara *et al.*² and Hoeflich *et al.*³ employed potentiostripping analysis (PSA) for thallium determination in environmental samples at natural levels. Differential pulse anodic stripping voltammetric (DPASV) determination of thallium has also been described. Human hair samples have been analysed for thallium content by Cizewski *et al.*⁴. Dhaneshwer *et al.*⁵ used tartrate buffer in presence of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid for the determination of thallium and a number of ions in biological materials. The utility of glassy carbon⁶ and mercury thin film⁷ electrodes in the determination of thallium has also been reported. The authors have suggested a simple, routine, differential pulse polarographic (DPP) method for the determination of thallium in presence of commonly occurring cations. D.C. polarography and cyclic voltammetry were also employed to investigate the electrochemical behaviour of thallium ion. The main aim of the work was to develop suitable analytical procedures for monitoring certain toxic trace metals in effluent samples.

Fig. 1. (a) DC polarogram of a solution containing $1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M Tl}^I$ in acetate buffer (pH 4.5) and (b) blank solution of acetate buffer.

Results and Discussion

Electrochemical behaviour of Tl^I was investigated in different supporting electrolytes, such as potassium chloride, potassium nitrate, ammonium chloride and acetate buffer. The polarographic characteristics of thallium reduction are given in Table 1. Thus acetate buffer (pH 4.5) was chosen for further studies, where a single DC polarographic wave was obtained at -0.48 V (Fig. 1).

Table 1. Polarographic characteristics of thallium reduction in different supporting electrolytes

Sl. No.	Supporting electrolyte	$E_{1/2}$ V	i μA
1.	0.1 M KCl	-0.52	4.5
2.	0.1 M KNO_3	-0.50	4.8
3.	0.1 M NH_4Cl	-0.51	4.2
4.	Acetate buffer (pH = 4.5)	-0.47	6.2

Cyclic voltammetry of thallium in acetate buffer was performed at different scan rates to investigate the reversible nature of electrode process, resulting in anodic as well as cathodic peaks ($E_{pc} = -0.55 \text{ V}$; $E_{pa} = -0.63 \text{ V}$ at scan rate, 60 mV/s), as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammogram of a solution containing $\text{Tl}^I = 1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, acetate buffer (pH 4.5), scan rate = 60 mV s^{-1} W.E. HMDE.

Thallium also gave a sharp DP peak in acetate buffer at a potential of -0.47 V . The peak current was found to increase linearly with the concentration of thallium in the range $0.05\text{--}24.60 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$. The characteristics of calibration curve were as follows: slope = 0.3011 ± 0.003 , coefficient of correlation (r) = 0.9991 , and standard deviation

(sd) = 0.1175. However, concentrations were determined by standard addition method⁸.

Interference : The interference of commonly occurring cations such as Cu^{II} , Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} (1.0 mg dm^{-3}) each, in DPP determination of thallium was studied at trace levels. DP peak potentials for Cu^{II} (-0.07), Tl^{I} (-0.47), Cd^{II} (-0.65) and Zn^{II} (-1.10 V) are distinguishable. The interference of coexisting metal ions (Hg^{II} , Pb^{II} , In^{III} and Sn^{IV}) in industrial effluent was also checked. Lead showed significant interference because DP peaks of lead and thallium were

Fig. 3. DP polarogram of a solution containing Cu^{II} , Tl^{I} , Cd^{II} and Zn^{II} (1.0 mg dm^{-3} each) in acetate buffer (pH 4.5); modulation amplitude = 50 mV, pulse duration = 57 ms, clock time of pulse = 1 s, scan rate = 5 mV s^{-1} .

noticeably close. Ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) was added to the test solution to eliminate the lead interference. A typical DP polarogram of a solution containing copper, thallium, cadmium and zinc is shown in Fig. 3.

The limit of determination achieved was found to be 50 mg dm^{-3} .

Procedure : DP peak of thallium in acetate buffer was made the basis for determination of thallium in synthetic samples and industrial wastes. Pretreated samples were taken into polarographic cell and DP polarograms were recorded in potential range from 0.0 to -0.7 V . Peak currents were measured at -0.48 V after making blank corrections. Results of polarographic determination indicate that the recovery of thallium is quantitative (average recovery 99.6%). In this manner, industrial wastes of Jodhpur city were analysed and thallium was not found in these samples.

Experimental

A polarographic analyser (174-A) in conjunction with a drop-timer (174/70) of EG & G, was used for D.C. and DPP experiments. A dropping mercury electrode (DME) was used as the working electrode. The instrumental settings for DPP were as follows : pulse amplitude, 50 mV; clock time of pulse, 1 s; pulse duration, 57 ms; scan rate, 5 mV s^{-1} . Potential was measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). Cyclic voltammetry was performed on a cyclic voltammograph (CV-27 of Bioanalytical Systems) with a hanging mercury drop electrode and Ag/AgCl as the working and reference electrodes respectively. Initial and final potentials were -0.2 and -0.85 V . The scan rate was varied from 20 to 100 mV s^{-1} . A platinum wire was used as the auxiliary electrode.

Industrial effluent samples were filtered to separate suspended particulate matter. To this aliquot (100 ml) an oxidising mixture (1 ml) of nitric acid and sulphuric acid was added and contents were heated till the solution fumed to remove organic matrices.

All experiments were made at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. Test solutions were deaerated for 20 min by passing pure nitrogen.

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